

Notes

Oxidimetric Estimation of Arginine, Histidine and Threonine with Chloramine-T

D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and N. M. MADE GOWDA

Department of Post-graduate Studies and Research in Chemistry, Manasagangotri, University of Mysore, Mysore-570006.

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CHLORAMINE-T (CAT) has received considerable attention as a new oxidant in the estimation of compounds of biochemical origin¹⁻³. Essential amino acids such as histidine and threonine serve important functions in our biological system and play a significant role in metabolism. These amino acids are used in biochemical, microbiological and nutrition investigations and are employed as dietary supplements. Arginine and histidine find applications in medicine and pharmaceuticals. In view of the importance of these amino acids, it was found to be of interest to develop suitable analytical techniques for their quantitative estimation. In the present work, we have examined the behaviour of CAT as an oxidant for the estimation of arginine, histidine and threonine. It was found that these amino acids undergo oxidation by CAT at room temperature in several solvent media. However, a stoichiometric oxidation with a four-electron change per mole was noticed in sulphuric acid medium (0.02–0.10 N). Back titration procedures were adopted as the reactions were not instantaneous, for a direct titration of the amino acid with CAT.

Experimental

Chromatographically pure L-Arginine hydrochloride, L-Histidine hydrochloride and L-Threonine were supplied by the V. P. Chest Institute, New Delhi. They were further recrystallized from aqueous solution and the purity was checked by the standard acetous perchloric acid method⁴. Solutions of amino acids (~2 mg/ml) were prepared in appropriate buffers and solvents. Chloramine-T (E. Merck) was purified by the method of Morris et al⁵ and an approximately decinormal solution was standardized by the iodometric method. Compounds of accepted grades of purity were used in preparing other solutions. Aqueous solutions were generally prepared in deaerated triply distilled water.

Recommended procedure :

Aliquots of aqueous amino acid solutions were added to 50 ml of 0.1 N CAT containing an overall concentration of H₂SO₄. Arginine : 0.05–0.25 N ; Histidine : 0.02–0.03 N ; Threonine : 0.025–0.075 N ; The reaction mixture was shaken occasionally and set aside for definite time intervals (Arginine HCl 30 min., Histidine HCl 60 min. and Threonine 90 min.). Then 20ml of 20% KI was added and the liberated iodine was titrated against standard thiosulphate using starch

indicator. A blank titration was carried out with the same volume of CAT in each case.

The amount (x mg) of the amino acid present in the experimental solution is given by

$$x = \frac{M}{4} N(V_1 - V_2)$$

where M is the molecular weight of amino acid, N is the normality of thiosulphate, V₁ is the blank titre and V₂ the volume of thiosulphate used for back titration.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of oxidation of arginine, histidine and threonine by CAT can be represented as follows :

where R is (NH₂)C(NH)NH(CH₂)₃ for arginine, (HC)N–CH=C(NH)CH₂ for histidine and CH₂CHOH for threonine.

The presence of *p*-toluene sulphonamide (R_F = 0.905) in the reaction mixture was detected by paper chromatography using benzyl alcohol saturated with water as solvent, with 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ethanol as the spray reagent. Nitriles formed were detected by their colour reaction⁶ with hydroxyl amine and ferric chloride.

The results are accurate within 0.5%. Presence of foreign ions such as Na⁺, Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺Cl⁻ and PO₄³⁻ (~0.2 mole) had no effect on the stoichiometry or rate of reaction. However, amino acids, cystine, methionine and valine interfere with the estimation, when present in amounts ~0.1 m mole.

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References

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